

1. Frequency distribution of BI scores to race IH-1 in the F₂ of crosses between susceptible Tongil and moderately resistant Dourado Precose and OS6. IRRI, 1984.

2. Frequency distribution of BI score to race IH-1 in the F₂ of the crosses between the highly resistant Milyang 54 and moderately resistant Dourado Precose and OS6. IRRI, 1984.

varied from 0 to 4. Most of the F₂ plants of Milyang 54/Dourado Precose were highly resistant. The reaction scores of most of the F₂ plants of

Milyang 54/OS6 ranged from 2 to 6. However, some highly susceptible segregants were observed for both.

We concluded that the moderate resistance to B1 race IH-1 in Dourado Precose and OS6 is conveyed by major genes with some modifiers. □

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Sheath rot (ShR) in Chhatisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, India

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ShR was first observed in Chhatisgarh in 1978 kharif. Disease incidence has increased, and has significantly reduced yields in some areas. In 1980-82, we field tested several important, commercially grown rice varieties for ShR resistance, based on the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES) 0-9 scale. Observations were recorded at late tillering to dough stage (see table).

Kranti, Phalguna, Surekha, Pragati, Jaya, Bangoli, and Ratna were infected most severely, particularly in 1981 kharif (20°-30°C temperatures, 65-80% relative humidity). There were many cloudy days during booting. In Phalguna and Kranti, 5-10% of the panicles did not emerge and extensive rotting of the sheaths enclosing the panicles caused significant yield losses. However, Asha, Usha, Safri 17, Dubraj, and Madhuri had some resistance (see table).

The ShR pathogen *Sarocladium oryzae* also causes glume discoloration alone or in combination with other fungi. Highly ShR-susceptible varieties such as Kranti and Phalguna were equally prone to grain discoloration. □

ShR incidence and glume discoloration (GID) in Chhatisgarh, India.

Variety	Disease incidence score ^a during					
	1980		1981		1982	
	ShR	GID	ShR	GID	ShR	GID
Safri	0	0	3	1	3	1
Kranti	7	1	9	7	7	5
Samridhi	3	1	5	3	3	1
Phalguna	5	1	9	7	5	7
Surekha	3	1	7	5	5	3
Pragati	7	3	-	-	5	3
Jaya	3	1	7	5	5	3
Bangoli	-	-	7	3	5	3
Asha	-	-	0	0	3	1
Usha	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ratna	5	1	7	5	5	3
Garima	-	-	-	-	3	1
Madhuri	-	-	3	1	3	1
Dubraj	-	-	0	0	0	1

^aBased on 1980 SES scale.